

**Sanskrit Medical Manuscripts in Harvard
University Library
Dominik Wujastyk
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Kārajñāna / Śambhu With *Hindī ṭikā*

Poleman no. 5321. Houghton Library shelf no. 1364.

FF. 1–37. 10×21cm. 8 lines, 25 akṣaras. Physically incomplete. .

Bibliography: Meulenbeld, HIL; Wujastyk, HSPM 1.741–745;
Wujastyk, MeSS 56.

Approximately 125 verses, whose numbering is confused. One
sequence runs from 1–83, another then runs from 25–67. No
division into samuddeśas.

F.1r has in pencil: kārajñāna khaṃ.

Begins, f.1v: śrīgaṇeśāya namaḥ //

kārajñānakalāyuktaṃ śambhonāthaś ca bhāṣitaṃ

yena ṣaṇmāsata pūrvvaṃ jñāyate mṛtyūrogināṃ // 1 //

ṭikā // kāla kahi iṃ maraṇa kalā kahi oṃlakṛṇa kahi oṃ //

śambhūnāthaccabhāṣitaṃ kahi iṃ // mahādeva pārvati ke āgaim

kahi hai rogamarṇa kā samaya kahi yeṃ naṣaṇamāsata purvvaṃ ke

hi iṃ pahilāṃ cha mahine ke agā urogī kā maraṇa mālum ka raim //

...

śloka kāla srjati bhūtāni kālaṃ saharate prajā //

kāla svapneḥ jāgartti kālo hi [f.2r] duritaḥ kramaḥ // 2 //

Final verse, f.37r–37v: atha śloka

uragavaraṇarūdrāvāsaveṃdratripūrvvā //

yamadahanaviśākhā pāyavāreṇa yuktvātithiṣu navamī ṣaṣṭī [f.37v]

dvādaśībhi caturthī // sahajamarāṇayogo / rogināṃ mṛtyukāla 67 /

ṭikā uraga kahi iṃ // aśleṣā varuṇa kahi oṃ ādrā // vāsava śrī

pūrvvā kahi oṃ viśākhā tripūrvvā kahi yai // ... // 67 //

[Text ends, 37v:] oha yogaji vārai āvai nivārai jāṇi oṃ //

arogīmukara āvamechāramēṃ caṃdramāvādyāti caṃdramā kā

yogapāvai //

Rasacintāmaṇi / Anantadeva Sūri Poleman no. 5288. Houghton Library
shelf no. 451.

Ff.10–11, 18–38, 40, 42–43, 50–51. 21.5×12.5cm. 24 lines, 16
akṣaras/line. Bottom edge of MS torn, with damage to text.

Physically incomplete. .

Bibliography: Printed at Bombay in 1911, with a Hindī *tīkā* and at Poona in 1925 with a Marāṭhī commentary.

. Title from section colophons.

A work on alchemy in eleven *stavakas*, which is quoted by Ṭoḍaramalla (fl. 1565/1589) in the *Āyurvedasaukhya* of his Ṭoḍarānanda (see NCC 1.168b, 169b) and in the *Bhāvaprakāśa* (16th century; see Jolly 1977, p.4 which may, however, refer to Rāmacandra's treatise of this name). Text incomplete.

check

Begins, f.10r: ṛṭyamaṃ yāvat śvitrakuṣṭhaṃ vināśayet //
vibhidyaṃnyakānīlāṃ nirvraṇasthūlapattakāṃ //
nirdoṣaṃ tālakaṃ tasyā madhye dattvātha mudyate //
F10r has: iti rasaciṃtāmaṇau śvitratāla'ke'ścaraḥ // ...
iti kṛṣṇasarpatailāśvitre //

F.11v has: iti rasaciṃtāmaṇau viśveśvaro nāma rasaḥ //

F.11v ends: dehī vīkṣya sukhaṃ mukhaṃ na virasaṃ vijñāya saṃyak
sudhī //

chāgīmūtravihāyana [breaks off]

F.18r begins: nāṃ viśeṣataḥ //

tilatailena tatsākaṃ vaṭakīnāṃ ca bhakṣaṇaṃ //

F.18r has: ity aṣṭādaśakuṣṭhāni satyaprayoga ekah //

F.24r has: iti śrībhiṣaganaṃtadevasūriviracite rasacitamaṇau śvitre
satyapratīkāraḥ //

F.38v has: iti śrīsiddhahemaguṭikā //

F.38v ends: tāramudrāṃ samānīyamukhavākhyena śoṣyate //
punar aṃtarena taṃ dattvā mukha [breaks off]

F.40r begins: guḍeṇa ca samanvitaṃ //

śoṣayec cātape piṣṭvā – — ślakṣṇa vicarpayet //

ekaviṃśadinaṃ yāvad bhāvanādi na suṃdarāḥ //

F.40r has: iti rasaciṃtāmaṇau haimīkaraṇaprayogaḥ //

F.40v has: iti rasaciṃtāmaṇau hemīkaraṇaprayogaḥ // ...

iti tārakṣṇī //

F.40v ends: sarāvasya puṭe kṛtvā maṃdāgnis tatra dīyate //

āraṇṇyaṃ śālakai'ḥ' paścāt tāra ā [$\frac{1}{3}$ line missing] yate ca tat //
kanakena samaṃ de [breaks off]

F.42r begins: dāruṇaṃ //

pītaṃ chaviṃ bhavet kiṃcit tat tāmraṃ nīya cottamaṃ //

F.42r has: atha hīrakamāraṇaṃ //

F.43v ends: iti tāmravarṇahemakaraṇaprayogarasah //

ॐ tamkaikaṃ kurute nāgaṭaṃkatāmraśuddhimat //
 daradaṃ bhāgāṃ mṛdo mūṣā tasyā tad astu dīyate //
 galite maṃdhaṣṭakāṣṭakena vā // [x]rśyaṃte dīyate naṃ ca maṃda
 – – vidhīyate [tear] kaṃ hema //
 F.50r begins: paṃcavelaṃ karīpuṭaiḥ //
 karīsaṃjāyate sāksād udayārkasamaṃ chaviḥ // ...
 iti rasaciṃtāmaṇau tārapītīkaraṇaprayogaḥ
 F.51v has: iti rasaciṃtāmaṇau pittīkaraṇaṃ //
 F.51v ends: iti jalajaṃtraprayogasiddhi /
 tolakaṃ tritayaṃ nāgaṃ retaye [tear] gataṃ //
 kālasaṃbhītaṃ tathā tolātra [tear] //
 dugdhikā veda ṭaṃka [tear] t //
 bhāvīyate ca tra [tear]
 F.51v has a marginal note in pencil: tru[ṭitam]. 18–25—18 750

A collection of medical recipies Poleman no. 5333. Houghton Library shelf no. 253.

Ff.4–6. 14×30.5cm. 11 lines, 46 akṣaras. Physically incomplete. .
 . Variant title: Called *Vaṅgakalpa* by Poleman, after note on cover.
 Outer cover has: [[317 260]]253 vaṃgakalpādi pa. 3–11–38 ślo.50.
 Begins, f.4r: śrīkṛṣṇāya namaḥ // atha viśaharaṇamaṃtraḥ //
 oṃ kālo vichakatriyālāsonānīpāṃcarūpāno pannārovīṭchu uttaraitau
 utārūṃ na hi tau garuḍamor ahaṃkāruṃ vṛścika
 āvaigomorakhāyegotoḍavichū utaretau hākahalolākarai merī bhakti
 guru kī śakti puro maṃtro śvarovācā //
 maṃtreṇānena maṃtrajño bhūtyākaragrhitayā /
 mārjayan maṃtram uccārya saptakṛtvā trivāraṃ 21 //
 sadyo nirviṣānāryā †ku'nnaraṃ vṛścikadaṃśitaṃ /
 varhipichādinā vāpi mārjayan nāśayed viṣaṃ // athāparo
 vṛścika[[ha]]viśaharaṇamaṃtraḥ // oṃ nalopanaḍaro //
 mārjayan mukhavātena maṃtreṇānena maṃtravit
 †tīśrorekhā prakuryyāt tu saralā bhuvī cātmanaḥ /
 ... athopaviṣāni //
 F.5r has: iti kṣāradvayaṃ dhīmān nyuktakāryeṣu yojayet //
 iti kṣārakalpanā // ity āyurvedāt //
 śrīkṛṣṇāya namaḥ // atha lakṣmīvilāsarasaḥ //
 palaṃ kṛṣṇābhracūrṇasya tadarddhaṃ rasagaṃdhakaṃ
 Ends, f.6v: raṃbhāprasūnaṃ tvāṃgerīmayachaṃ kadalīphalaṃ
 navanītaṃ tathā kṣāro raṃbhyaṃgasnīnam ācāret //
 iti vaṃgakalpa //

F.121r has: iti dullabhasūnugaṇakṛte siddhayogasamgraha
uttarasthāna samāptaṃ // samāptaś cāyaṃ
munimatānuvahaṃyogasamgraha
F.172v ends: maṃtraim̐vedodiviprasādīcalanabhāṣitaṃ / aśva †
yathasimasijaścavavesamodrasya dvārevakreṇetiṣṭhāmīti † svasti
māṃsaṃ pādāye // samāptaś cāyaṃ graṃtha iti
aśvāyurvedagaṇakṛta iti nāmaḥ //

Vaidyavallabha / Hastiruci With *Ṭīkā in Gujarātī (Poleman)*

Poleman no. 5334. Houghton Library shelf no. 2269.

Ff.1–18. 11.5×26.5cm. mūla: 6 lines, 37 akṣaras; ṭīkā: 9 lines, 40.
Interlinear Ṭīkā. Physically incomplete. .

Complete in eight chapters. Outer wrapper has: [[338 279]] 2269
vaidyajīvanasābā. pa.18 ślo. 1000 [and in pencilled Roman script:]
vaidyavalabha.

Text begins, f.1v: //90// sarasati hṛdhi'diṃ' dhyātvā natvā
śrīgurupatkajaṃ

sad hastirucinā vai'dya'vallabho yaṃ vidhīyate 1
purvavaidyena vidhinā vidhāya roganirṇayaṃ paścāt sāthyaṃ yathā
jñātvā taṃ tobhaiṣajam ārabhet 2

Commentary begins, f.1v: sarasatine namaskāra karīne śrī gurune
namaskāra karīne vaidyasāsraprakāśakarau vaidyavalabha 1
pahilu vaidyai vidhe karīne togano nirṇayakarī pache
sūdhārogajāṇīnaṃ valato uṣadhakare 2

Text ends, f.18r: 24

sakṣaudre tāvalehotha patreṇa bhaṣayet sadā
vātapītodbhavāṃ pīḍāṃ praṇasyati pravesanāt 25
iti vaidyavalabhe viracyate mahāvaidyakasāstara saṃpūrṇa 8
saṃvat 1845 varṣe phāguṇasūda [in a smaller hand:] 6 vārabūdhe
bhaṭāraka śrī śrī śrī 108 śrī munendrasomasūri [[ta paṃ]] śiṣya
suṣarājajī paṃ. mujirājajī celā premarājalapīkṛtaṃ //
bharatamadhye gāṃma //

Ṭīkā ends, f.18r: madhasaṃ avalehī atha vāmāṃ naṣāṃ
īvāyanīpitanī saṭktenī jāṃ 25 iti vaidyavalabhe viracyate
māhāvīadyakasāstra samāptaṃ 8 //

yādrasaṃ pustake dṛvāṃ tadrasaṃ laṣitaṃ mayā
yadi sūdham asūdham vā mama doṣo na dīyate 1 //
śloka laṣyo che // śrī //

F.18v has marginal note: 18-†5-20 1000

Ajīrṇamañjarī / Kāśīnātha Poleman no. 5295. Houghton Library shelf no. 530a.

Ff.1–3. 13×28.5cm. 5–6 lines, 28 akṣaras. Physically incomplete. .

. Variant title: Amṛtamañjarī.

This was formerly thought to be part of the same text as the *Dravyagaṇaśataślokī* which follows it (see MS 530b), and was so catalogued by Poleman. Covers only 12 verses of the work. Sanskrit interlinear gloss throughout. F.1r has: 28–5–28 350.

Begins, f.1v: svasti śrīgaṇeśāya namaḥ //

yo rāvaṇaṃ raṇamukhe bhuvanaikahāraṃ hatvā cakāra jagataḥ
paramopakāraṃ //

yaṃ vraṃhmaṇau “bhidadhire parato “pi pāraṃ

taṃ naumi [gloss: ‘haṃ kāśīnātha] maithalasutāhṛdayaikahāraṃ //

1 //

nālikeraphaleṣu taṃdula jalaṃ kṣīraṃ rasāle hitaṃ

jaṃvīrottharaso ghr̥te samucitaḥ sarppis tu mocāphale /

godhūmeṣu ca karkaṭī hitatamāṃ māṃsā[f.2r]tyaye kām̐jikam̐

nāraṃge guḍabhakṣaṇaṃ prakathitaṃ piṃḍāluke kodravaṃ //

Ends, f.3v: kaserū śṛṅgāṭamṛṇālamṛdvikharjūrakhaṃḍāpi ca

nāgareṇa [breaks off in verse 12]

Rasamañjarītantra / Śālinātha Poleman no. 5313. Houghton Library shelf no. 244.

Ff.1–72 (two subsidiary foliation sequences, 33–57 = 1–25; 58–72 = 1–15, probably distinguishing the work of three different scribes.). 14×30.5cm. 7 lines, 26 akṣaras. Ff.24 & 25, 27 & 28 34 & 35, 36 & 37, 38 & 39 stuck together.. Physically incomplete.

Outer wrapper has: [crossed out: 296 [red ink:] 251] [red ink:] 244 rasamañjarītantraṃ – śālināthaḥ pa. 12–10–27 ślo. 800.

Begins, 1r: śrīgaṇeśāyanamaḥ atha rasamañjarī likhyate //

yad gaṃḍamaṃḍalagalanmadavārivim̐dupānālasātinibhṛtā lalitā
limālā //

sadguṃjītena vinahaṃti navedranīlaḥ śahāṃ sa vo gaṇapati śivam
ātanotu // 1 //

F.32v ends: iti lohamāraṇaṃ // iti

śrīpaṃḍitavaidyanāthasutaśrīśālināthavirciṃte [sic]

rasamañjarītantraṃ svarṇādīdhātuśodhanamāraṇakathanam̐ nāma
paṃcamo dhyāyaḥ 5 //

F.33r begins: kṣīrādhver utthitaṃ devaṃ pītavastraṃ caturbhujam̐

vaṃde dhanvaṃtariṃ nityaṃ nānāgadaniṣudanaṃ 1
 This section ends, after 355 verses, on f.55v: iti rase
 dharmādharmanirṇayaḥ iti
 śrīpaṃḍitavaidyanāthathanayaśrīśā^oviracete rasamaṃjarītaṃtre
 rasakathanaṃ nāma ṣaṣṭo dhyāyaḥ Ends, f.72r: iti
 śrīpaṃḍittavaidyanāthathanayaśrīśālināthaviracite
 rasamaṃjijaḥrītaṃtre kālajñānādikathana nāma daśamo dhyāya 10
 iti samāpta rasamaṃjarītaṃtra samāptaṃ śuddhaṃ
 tutthaṃmāhuliṃgadraveṇa bhāvyam vārān ekaviṃśakrameṇa ekaṃ
 cakṣuḥ pūrayed aṃjanena caikaṃ hy aṃgaṃ jāyate vijaratvaṃ 1
 yādṛśaṃ pustakaṃ dṛṣṭvā tādṛśaṃ likhitaṃ mayā
 yadi śuddham aśuddham vā mama doṣo na dīyate 2
 soraṭhāḥ //
 kaimḍisaṃkaṭamāhi[f.72v:]cyāradānājonā banaiṃ
 ekadānākarisāhikī je bheṣajadānato 1
 laṣkarikarītrasiddha lālacamḍapāsamadri kaimḍ gāvapuvālyāmadhya
 samāpatā rasamaṃjarī 2
 mādhasukalā pakṣadītavāra tithi paṃcamī
 saṃmatajāṃniprataḥṣabāṇavyomabhūṣaḍasasi 3

Madanavinodanirghaṇṭu / Madanapāla Poleman no. 5300. Houghton Library shelf no. 504.

Ff.1–84, 2 leaves, 87–98, [9]9, then in a different hand, [100]–101, and in a different hand again, 102–103. 12.5×26.5cm. 9–12 lines, 28 akṣaras. Ff.84–85, 89–[100] are torn at top right hand side of recto. Ff.[100]–103 were evidently copied after the rest of the manuscript; the repetition of the torn end of f.99 at the beginning of f.[100] established that the final leaves added to complete a damaged text. It is strange that f.[100] is also torn in the same place as the preceding leaves. Physically incomplete. . Margins, section and chapter colophons in red ink. Found with Paper wrapper has: madanavinodanirghaṇṭuḥ madanpāla – 103 – 5 – 32 sa – 1874 ślo 1850.

Bibliography: Meulenbeld, HIML.

Madanapāla (fl. 1375/1400) was a member of the great Ṭāka family which ruled Kāṣṭhā on the Yamunā, north of Delhi. The family history is outlined at the end of the *Madanavinodanirghaṇṭu*, and at the beginning of the *Rasaratnadīpa* of Rāmarāja (a descendant of Madanapāla). Called *Madanavinodanirghaṇṭu* in manuscript; marginal initials: nirghaṇṭa^o. Variant titles: *Madanapālanirghaṇṭu*,

Madanavinoda, Madanapālavinodanighaṅṭu, Madananighaṅṭu and probably Madanaratnanighaṅṭu. (ADSaṃ 1874 (date of correction)).

Covers all 13 vargas.

Begins, f.1v: śrīdhanvaṃtarāya namaḥ //

jīvaṃ śrutīnāṃ sudhanaṃ munīnāṃ // bījaṃ guṇānāṃ mahad
ādikānāṃ

āgnyeyam astrāṃ bhavapātakānāṃ // kiṃcin mahāśyāmalam
āśrayāmi // 1 //

F.84v ends (near the beginning of the 11th varga): vicārya tadguṇān
etāṃs tadguṇān eva nir[+ + +; text breaks off]

First unnumbered leaf begins: gurulaghuyūṣas tapyaṃtu sūpyako
bhr̥ṣṭaiḥ /

siṃvijair nistuṣaikṛtaiḥ / [breaks off]

Ends: nirmmathya / paṭe śarkarayānviṭaṃ / savyoṣadāḍimājājih
sadr̥ko[breaks off]

Second unnumbered leaf begins: ko rocanaḥ / svaryaḥ pittānilaharo
guruḥ /

dīpanas tarppaṇo valpaḥ //[tear; then a section colophon:] haḥ
saddakguṇāḥ

Ends: [tear]lpo / kṣatajihvaṃ haṇaḥ paraḥ ghevaraguṇāḥ / samitā
sarppiṣā bhr̥ṣṭā śve[breaks off]

F.87r begins: ailālavaṃgakarppūracūrṇādiparisam̐skṛtaṃ /
kṣiptvānyasamitālamba / puṭeṣu sughr̥te pacet

F.98v ends (near the beginning of the 13th varga) and [9]9r starts:
bhojanānam̐taram̐ nidrā / vātaghnā kaphapuṣṭikṛ / t

kaphamedoviṣā [f.[9]9r starts] rttānāṃ / rātrau jāgaraṇaṃ hitaṃ
F.99v ends: tarūṇāṃ pallavādayaḥ

varddham̐te pi tathā nnr̥ṇāṃ śneha[tear] [text breaks off]

F.[100]r begins: śnehāvagāhanaṃ vāt'sa'manaṃdhātupuṣṭidaṃ
mātrābh̐is tricatuḥpaṃcaṣaṣaptāṣṭābh̐ir āvrajet 77[torn]

F.103r has: abde vrahmajagaṭjjege[m̐]ṭdugaṇite

śrīvikramārkaprabho

nodyemāsivalakṣapakṣalaliteṣadyāṃ sudhāṃseṭdine

dīnānāṃ paritāpapāpadalno graṃthaṃ nighaṃtukhalūḥ

śrīdaḥ śrīmadano vyadhata caturaḥ sacchatracūḍāmaṇiḥ 12

anavadyāni yadyāniṃdasadvādasāvāpi vā

pareṣāṃ aticeṣāṃcit lihitomihakautukāt 13

yo rājñāṃ muṣatilakaḥ kaddāramallas tena śrīmadanar̐peṇa

nirm̐mite tra graṃthe bhūn madanavinodanāṃni pūr̐ṇo vargo yalita

yadaḥ prasastivargaḥ nāmomṛtarasaḥ pradāṃram asti [half a line

whited out] 14

Colophon, f.103r: samāpto yaṃ madanavinodaṅnirghaṃṭuḥ // //

śrīr astu // śrī //

pothī suddha kījī saṃvat 1874 kā miti mhāsudi 5 maṃgalavāranai //
yo [breaks off]

F.103v has: laṃ^o 38 [and in pencil] 103-4-32 1850

Kūṭamudgara / Mādhava Poleman no. 5303. Houghton Library shelf
no. 46.

Ff.1–5, 7. 13.5×27cm. 12 lines, 32 akṣaras. Physically incomplete. .

Editions: Printed at Bombay in 1884, with a commentary by Kṛṣṇa
Śāstrī Bhāṭavaḍekar; at Colombo in 1889, with a Siṃhalese
translation by D. J. Rubern Jayatunga; at Bombay in 1900 with a
paraphrase in Sanskrit and a Hindī commentary by
Rāmāpratāpaśarman; at Bombay in 1909/10, with a Hindī
commentary by Muralīdharaśarmā; at Muktyala in 1917, in Telugu
script, with Telugu translation. Bibliography: Meulenbeld, HIL. With
(auto?)commentary. Outer cover has: kūṭamudgāra mādhava – pa
7–12–35 śloka 175.

Begins, f.1r: // śrī gaṇeśāya namaḥ

kaphavātau vātakaphau vātaḥ pittaṃ ca vṛddhiśamau

tribhir ādyais tribhir aṃtyais tribhir ādyaparais tad anyais ca 1

madhuram nilavaṇakaṭutiktakaṣāyāḥ . . .

F.5v ends (in commentary on v.15): tad uktaṃ

ātmā manasā yujyate mana imdriyam artheneti svasthasyaiva rūpā

F.7r begins (in commentary on v.17: sya pākvartham agne

dīpanatvāt yuktā

Ends, f.7v: spaṣṭaṃ bhiṣajā mādhavenedaṃ ki jñānenālpadarśinā

yatkimcid uktam ajñānāt tatkaśamadhva manīṣiṇaḥ 21

kiṃ jñānena niṃdyajñānena alpadarśinā alpādhyayanena

etenātmanaḥ savinayatv amuktaṃ

Colophon, f.7v: iti mādhavaviracitaḥ kūṭamudgaraḥ cha // śrī //

F.7v has, in the margin, in pencil: 7–12–35 175

Rogavinīścaya / Mādhava Poleman no. 5304. Houghton Library shelf
no. 221.

Ff.11–108. 14×32cm. 7 lines, 40 akṣaras. New hand begins on f.20.
Physically incomplete. .

. Variant title: Mādhavanidāna. Marginal glosses on ff.1–16. Outer
wrapper has [crossed out: 269 227] 221 mādhavanidānaṃ p.

98.7.38 ślo – 1600.

Begins, f.11r: huśo bhuktamāmameva vimuṃcati 64

atīsāre nivṛtte pi maṃdāgner ahitāsinaḥ

bhūyaḥ saṃdūṣito vahnir grahaṇīm abhidūṣayet 65

Ends, f.108v: biddhadvirvraṇaso thaś ca dvau vraṇau

bhagnanādikau

bhagaṃdaro 'padaṃśaiva śūkadoṣadyumāgayāḥ // 12 //

yat sūtrasukṛtaṃ kiṃcit kṛtvaikaṃ yiniścayaṃ mucaṃjumaṃtavaḥ

stena nityam ātaṃkasamṭati // 13 //

Colophon (red ink): iti śrīmādhavanidānaviracite

samastaśarīraroganidānaṃ saṃpūrṇaṃ // śrīr astu //

F.108v has a modern note in purple crayon: 98-7-38 ślo 1600.

Rugviniścaya / Mādhava Poleman no. 5332. Houghton Library shelf no. 433.

Ff.1–61. 11×25.5cm. 9 lines, 34 akṣaras. Red ink used for marginal rulings. Thin, almost transparent, smooth paper. Hand (or pen) changes on f.5v, 45v, 59r. Physically incomplete. . Found with Extensive marginal glosses up to f.42r.

. Title from identified from opening verses. Outer wrapper has: [[65]] 433 roganidānaṃ — pa 61 ślā 875. Note reference to Gayadāsa in the gloss on f.42r.

F.1r has the following verse:

netraṡsyādhaḥ sphuraṇam asakṛtsaṃgare bhaṃgam āhuḥ

netrasyordhvaṃ harati sakalaṃ mānuṣaṃ duḥkhajālaṃ

netrasyāṃte bhavati ca dhanam nāstikāṃte ca mṛtyuḥ

vāme caitat phalam avikalaṃ dakṣiṇe vai parītyaṃ 1

Text begins, f.1v: //9pa// śrīgaṇeśāya namaḥ //

praṇamya jagadutpattisthitisamhārakāraṇam

svargāpavargayor dvāraṃ trailokyaśaraṇam śivam 1

nānā munīnām vacanair idānīm samāsataḥ sadbhiṣajām niyogāt

sopadravāriṣṭanidānalimgo nivadhyate graṃtha viniścayo 'yaṃ

Gloss at top edge of very fragile leaf, f.1v: atra praśabdena

graṃthakṛdbhaktyatiśayaṃ khyāpayati 1

bhuvanatrayasya rakṣitāraṃ 12 rogāṇām viniścayo ṡjñānam yasmāt

sa // 3

nanu sarvajñajñānaviṣaye paramasūkṣme nidānāditatvajñāne

sarvajñapuruṣavākya katham buddhimatam pravṛttir ity āhaḥ //

nānā munīnām kvanaih kṛtvā //

Gloss in left margin, f.1v: nānā munīnāṃ kvanair yogaṅrdvibhiḥ
traikālikajñānadarśī puruṣātīśayo munir ucyate // 2 agre tanaiḥ
ācāryaiḥ pūrvam evaṃ vidho graṃthasaṃgraho na kṛtaḥ ity arthaḥ
Gloss finishes on f.42r, with commentary on verse 633 of the mūla:
ātopaś calanaṃ iti **gayadāsaḥ** gujagujāśabdaḥ iti kārttikaḥ 3
atyugrarujaṃ / iti tīvravedanaṃ ādhmānaṃ vātapūrṇaṃ // 3 F.58v
has: iti aśmarīnidānaṃ // ... [leaf ends:] stāne ca pittaṃ
paridūśyavā
F.59r begins: pi
kṣīṇeṣu doṣeṣu ca kṣyadhātūn saṃdūśyamehān kurute nilāś ca
Text ends, f.61v, after 42 verses: 41 masūrikām āha //
masūrasaṃsthānasamāvijñeyā sā masūrikā 42
alajīm āha // raktāsītāspḥoṭacilā dāruṇā tv alajī bhava[t]
Marginal jotting, f.61v: 61–8–30 1304

Nāḍījñāna With *Hindī tīkā*

Poleman no. 5324. Houghton Library shelf no. 1365.

Ff.1–10. 10.5×20.5cm. Text: 4 lines, 21 akṣaras; commentary: 6
lines, 29 akṣaras. Physically incomplete. .

. Title from colophon of commentary.

Complete in 39 verses. Tripāṭha text.

F.1r has, in pencil, two floral flourishes and a note: nāḍīlakṣaṇa mū.
saṃ tī. bhā 120.

Text begins, f.1v: prathama nāḍīparīkṣā mutraparīkṣā dvitīyakaṃ //
trītiyaṃ kālaceṣṭaṃ caturthaṃ ceṣṭaśarīrakaṃ // 1 //
rogākrāntaśar[f.2r]īrasya sthānānyaṣṭau parīkṣayet
nāḍīmutramalaṃjihvāśabdasparsāś ca rupadrik // 2 //
saptaśatānāṃ madhyāc caturāyikā viṃśatiḥ
tāsām ekā parīkṣāyā dakṣīnakarena vinyastā // 3 // Commentary
begins: om śrīgaṇeśāya namaḥ prathama nāḍī lakṣaṇa ka hate hai //
prathama kaha ī nāḍīdeṣaṇīṅṣv iti yakahaṃ ī dusarīḥ / mutraparīkṣā
karaṇī // trītiya kaha ī trījokāljñāna // saiṃ kāla kā caturthaḥ
śarīrakā lakṣaṇa veṣa īḥ // 1 //

On f.7r, verses 24 and 25 are omitted from the text, but added in a
small marginal box.

Text ends, f.10v: yāti sukṣyā ca vakrā ca tām asādhyāṃ virdū vudhā
sirānāṃ lakṣasāṃ caiva vijñānīyād bhiṣagvadaiḥ // 39 //
iti nāḍīna saṃpūrṇaṃ // samāptam //

Commentary ends: jis kī nāḍī patalī cālai ṭeṭicālaiti samā nāḍī ko
asādhyā kahi jai nāḍī kā jñāna ye ha prakāseti deṣa kai vaidya

upacāraka rai // 39 // iti nāḍījñānaṃ saṃpūrṇaṃ // samāptam //

Nāḍīparīkṣā Poleman no. 5325. Houghton Library shelf no. 612.

Ff.1–4, 4^a. 13×23.5cm. 12 lines, 34 akṣaras; absorbent, tissue-like paper. Physically incomplete. .

. Title from Colophon of f.4^ar.

by Dulla son of Jānijayānaṃda.

There is a lacuna between leaves 4 and 4^a, in that the numbering of the verses returns to 37, but the verses 37 and 38 of f.4^a do not correspond to those on f.4r–4v. Note too, that there are two verses numbered 29, and the second falls across the join between leaves 3r and 4r. The hand, paper, margins and appearance of the leaves suggests that these leaves are nevertheless all part of a single manuscript. Outer wrapper has: [[242 242] 612 nāḍīparīkṣā pa.4 ślo. 40.

Begins, f.1r: śrīgaṇeśāya namaḥ // nāḍīpārīkṣām ākhyāsyāmaḥ //
snāyur nāḍī nasā hiṃsrā dhamanī dharaṇīdharā //
taṃttukī jīvanajñānākhirāparyāyavācakāṃ // 1 //
tiryak kūrmmmo dehināṃ nālīdeśe vāme vaktraṃ tasya pucchaṃ tu
yāmye //

ūrdhve bhāge hastapādaḥ ca vāmaḥ tasyaivādhaḥ saṃsthitau
dakṣiṇau ca // 2 //

F.2v has 3 blank lines, but no apparent lacuna. The scribe seems to have avoided writing over a part of verso of the leaf having show-through of writing from the recto.

F.2v ends: // 21 // kāṣṭhakūṭādī cakrāṇāṃ vicitragatisaṃginī //
sannipātoḥbha [tear]

F.3r begins: dviguṇaḥsraḥ tu tan maryādā smṛtā kramāt // 21 //

F.3r ends: caturdhā gaṃtūjaḥ śāpābhicārāveśadhā tataḥ //
pūrvayo bhūrivisphoṭamohā

F.3v blank.

F.4r begins: vāveśaje tu rūṭ // 29 //

tat tad bhūtasya kāmotthe ḥhī dhī svapnahati jvare //

dāhātisārauṣvedothe yathā svaghātajaṃ vaddet // 30 //

F.4v ends: vāmiḥ kṛcchraṃ jvaraḥ kāsasvāsasṛrāmohaśoṭharūk //

hikkārucīś ceti liṅgaṃ maraṇāyātisāriṇaḥ // 45

ity atirsarāvalokaḥ // //

gateti sārair thāmena duṣṭo cegra

F.4^ar begins: pittaṃ ca kaphasaṃyuktaṃ jñātavyaṃ vibudhair janaiḥ
stokaṃ vātakaphaṃ naṣṭapittaṃ vahati dāruṇaṃ //

pittaplāvamti jānīyāt bheṣajam tasya kārayet // 37 //
atyugraṃ vahate vāḥhayuḥ kapham ca kaṃḍasaṃyutaṃ //
naṣṭam pitte tu nāḍyā susannipāte lidhīyate // 38 //
iti sārōtidhāro graṃthe nāḍīparikṣā samāptā //
jānijayānamdātmajena duḥllena likhitā nāḍī // // cha // //
Jotting in purple crayon: ślo 40

Pathyāpathyādhikāra Poleman no. 5326. Houghton Library shelf no. 812.

Ff.1, 4–22. 11.5×23.5cm. 14 lines, 34 akṣaras. Physically incomplete. .

Copied in Narāyaṇānagara by Dhanarāja Matha, son of Vidyāvinoda. Outer cover has: [[201]] Jeypore [in red:] 812 Medicine Complete [in Devanāgarī] pathyāpathyavicāraḥ pa.22–16–32 ślo 700 sam.1748.

Begins, f.1v: e90 // śrīgaṇeśāya namaḥ // śrīdhanvaṃtarāya namaḥ //

śrīyārajaḥ satvatamāmsiviśvaṃ vinirmmitaṃ yakṣapatisvayaṃ yaḥ
aśeṣavṛṃdārakavṛṃdavaṃdyam / pāyādapāyān manujān girīśaḥ 1
ālokya vaidya taṃtrāṇi / yatrādoṣanibadhyate /
vyādhitanāṃ cikitsāsu pathyāpathyaviniścayaḥ 2
bhiṣaksarveṣu rogeṣu nirdiṣṭāni yathāyathaṃ
nidānāpathyapathyāni trīṇi yatrād vicimtayet 3

F.1v ends in the middle of verse 14: 13

purātanāḥ ṣaṣṭikaśālayaś ca vāttaḥkti saubhājanakāravellaṃ
caitrāgamāśādhaphalaṃ paṭolaṃ karkoṭakaṃ mūlakapotike ca /
mudgai

F.4r begins: rmasūraiś caṇakaiḥ kulatthai /
rma kuṣṭakair vātaharaiś ca yūṣaḥ

pāṭhāmṛtāvāstukataṃḍulīya / jīvaṃti śākāni ca kākamācī 15

F.2v has chapter colophon: iti jvararogapathyāpathyādhikāraḥ 1

Ends, f.22r: iti dūrvāditailaṃ // iti pathyāpathyādhikāraḥ samāptaḥ
saṃvat 1758 varṣe śāke 1823 pravarttamāne jyeṣṭhaśuklapaṃcamī
ravisutadine likhitaṃ // mathena vidyāvinodatatputradhanarājena
likhitaṃ svavācanārthaṃ graṃthāgraṃthaśloka 711 śrīdevagurvoḥ
prasādena sadājayastuḥ / śrīr astuḥ // narāyaṇānagaramadhye
liṣitaṃ /

F.22v has: 22–15–32 ślo 700

Sukhānandasūtrasthāna Poleman no. 5317. Houghton Library shelf no. 567.

Ff.1–7. 12×25.5cm. 15 lines, 35 akṣaras. Physically incomplete. .

Bibliography: CC 3.129. Marginal heading throughout:
sukhānaṃdasūtrasthānaḥ. Marginal note, f.7v: 7-15-35 slo. 200;
outer wrapping has [crossed out in red: 140] [in red:] 567
sūtrasthāna– pa. 7–15–35 ślo. 200 apūrṇa.

F.1r has a passage from Vāgbhaṭa in a different hand:

check

vāgbhaṭe saptamādhyāyasamāptau
snānānulepanahimānilakhaṃḍakhādya
śītāṃḍudugdharasapūṣasturāḥ prasannāḥ
seceta cānuśayanam viratau ratasya
tasyaivam āśu vapuṣaḥ punar eti dhāma // 1
śrutacaritasamṛddhe karmadakṣe dayālau
bhiṣaji niranuvamḍham deharakṣām niveśya /
bhavati vipulatejaḥ svāsthykīrttiprabhāvaḥ
svakuśalakulabhogī bhūmipālaś cirāyuh //
tathāṣṭamādhyāyasamāptau /
prasṛṣṭe vi mūtre hr̥di suvimale doṣe svapathage
viśuddhe codgāre kṣudapagamane vāte nusarati /
tathānnād udrikte viśadakaraṇe dehe ca sulaghau
prayujitāhāram vidhinyamitam phālasamahitaḥ //
ekādaśo dhyāya samāptau /
ya eva dehasya samāvivṛddhyaita eva doṣā viśamāvadhāya /
yasmād atas te hitacaryayaiva kṣayād vivṛdher api rakṣaṇīyāḥ
Begins, f.1v: //90// śrīgurubhyo namaḥ //
śrīmatsukhānaṃdarasāyanena dhanvaṃtariḥ siddhasudhīmayena
premaprasannaprasabhekṣaṇena saṃjīvayaty ārttajanam kṣaṇena 1
āyuh prārabdhavāyuprasarad api vidhir nānyathā karttum īso yad ye
py evam tathā py āgamanigamapaṭur dṛṣṭakarmābhiṣak cet dravyam
ced bhūrikalpaṃ śucicaturacarobuddha āḍhyogadīcet saṃcāro
vedanāyāḥ katham aparicayaḥ śrīsukhānaṃdarāḥ 2
syustvag 7 dhātū 7 papadhātvā 7 śaya 7 mala 7 kalikā 7
saptasaptātha saptasaty unmānāḥ sirāḥ 700 saptakasahitaśatam 107
marmasiddhā 2 44 manyāḥ trir doṣāḥ ṣoḍaśa 16 ca navaśatam 900
snāyavo splāṃ trisatyā 300 digyuktaṃdhi dviśatyā 210 saraśata 500
palapeśyaḥ striyas tatva 25 yuktāḥ 3
Ends, f.6v: kṣaudre gnyudyadguḍe
vāpputapuritasayoścr̥ṇṇapim̐ḍiguṭī syāt
śvetābdhighrāguḍo dviḥpuramadhusamam anyac ca dravyam
dvinighram lehaḥ kvāthādipākāt punar
ucitarasobdhighraśubhrāguḍodviḥ kṣepyo bdhighro dravo

nyoghapalamitamitiḥ snehasaṃdhānalehe 69
 sneho bdhighrāṃbupakvoṣadhacaraṇarasaḥ snehakalkau
 caturthāgnyās tailājye athātra dravaciranihitam
 vastusaṃdhānamuktaṃ kvāthaiḥ siddham tv ariṣṭam
 himajalanihatair āsavā kaṃguḍārdraṃ kṣaudrakṣepo daśāṃśo
 daśavidhakalanākalpanādravyamātre 70
 iti śrī sukhānaṃ[da]sūtrasthānakaṃ saṃ [tear]
 F.7r begins: atha mānaṃ
 yastrimtrā 30 t paramāṇubhis trasamukho reṇuḥ sa baṃśīti ca
 paryāyair iha kathyate ravikarair jālāṃtagair drśyate
 taiḥ ṣaḍbhis tu marīcikārasaguṇā tābhiḥ smṛtā rājikā
 tābhī rāmaguṇaḥ smṛtaḥ saraṣapo '8'ṣṭaghro yavaḥ sarṣapāt 1
 F.7v has: [marginal title:] sukhānaṃdasūtrasthānapatra
 ... yat tam ādyaṃ gaṇasya 10 iti māgadhaparibhāṣā
 ... iti mama dhiṣaṇā tu smṛtaṃ mānakalpaṃ 13 iti
 sāmānyaparibhāṣā //
 āstikyaṃ pravibhajya bhojanam anubhāpaś ca tathyaṃ vaco
 medhābuddhidhṛtikṣamās ca karuṇā jñānaṃ ca nirdaṃtatā
 karmā niṃditam asprḥaś ca vinayo dharmāḥ sa daivādarād
 ete satvaguṇānṅvitasya manaso gītāguṇājñānibhiḥ 1
 krodhas tāḍanaśīlatā ca bahulaṃ duḥkhaṃ sukhoṃcchādhikā
 daṃbhaḥ kāmukatāpy alīkavacaṇaṃ cādhīratāhamkṛtiḥ
 aiśvaryādy abhimānatātīsayitānaṃdo dhikaś cāṭanaṃ
 prakhyātāhiraḥ guṇena sahitasyaite guṇās cetasaḥ 2
 nāstikyaṃ viṣaye cchitātīsayitālasyaṃ ca duṣṭā matiḥ
 prītir niṃditakarmaśarmaṇi sadā nidrālutaḥarniśaṃ
 ajñānaṃ kila sarvato pi satataṃ krodhānvitā mūḍhadhīḥ
 prakhyātā hi tamoguṇena sahitasyaite guṇās cetasaḥ 3
 'jñātavyā pi tamoguṇena sahitasyaitāni cihnāni vai'

Suśrutasaṃhitā / Suśruta Poleman no. 5318. Houghton Library shelf no. 303.

Ff.1–72. 13×29cm. 33 akṣaras, 9 lines. F.43 torn almost in half. Physically incomplete. . Ff.36r, 54r, 64r have decorative borders.

Bibliography: Compared with the edition of Madhusūdana Gupta, *The Suśruta or System of Medicine Taught by Dhanwantari and Composed by his Disciple Suśruta* (Calcutta: (pp.1–378) Education Press, 1835; (pp.1–562) Baptist Mission Press, 1836), pp.378, 562. [Widener IndL 3561.9].

by Dharmadāsa.

Sections of the Sūtrasthāna and Nidānasthāna, but grossly mixed up. Possibly copied from an exemplar whose leaves were muddled, although no passages appear to start in mid sentence. Perhaps a physician's personal set of extracts. Brown paper wrapper has: [[395 320]] 303 vai. suśrutaḥ ślo.1200 pa. 72–9–30.

Begins, f.1v: //90// śrīgaṇeśāya namaḥ // oṃ namo
vrahmaprajāpatyaśvibalibhir
dhanvaṃtarisuśrutavāgbhaṭacamaḍraṭacarakādibhyo namaḥ // 1 //
athā[[tā]]yurvedotpattiṃ nāmādhyāyaṃ [=1] vyākhyāsyāmaḥ //
yathovāca bhagavān dhanvaṃtariḥ śuśrutāya //
dhanvaṃtariṃ dharmabhṛtām variṣṭam amṛtodbhavaṃ //
pādayor upasaṃgrhya suśrutaḥ paripṛchati // 1 // [this verse not in
edition]
atha khalu bhagavaṃtam amaravaram ṛṣigaṇaṃ parivṛ'ta'm
āśramasthaṃ kāsirājaṃ divaudāsaṃ dhanvaṃtarim aupadhenavaṃ
vaitaraṇaurabhṛapauṣkalāvatakaravīryagopurarakṣitasuśrutaprabhṛtayaḥ
ucuh //

F.5v has: sapuṇyakarmā bhuvī pūjyato nṛpaiḥ
rasakṣaye śakrasalokatām brajet // [the last verse of adhy.1, which is
more or less intact, textually.

Adhy.2 is skipped.]

iti sauśrute āyurvedaśāstre sūtrasthāne āyurvedotpattiṃ [=1]
nāmādhyāyo prathama // 1 //
athāto 'dhyayanasampradānīyam adhyāyaṃ [=3] vyākhyāsyāma //
śālākyatamaṃtraṃ kaumāraṃ cikitsā kāyakī ca yā /
bhūtavidyeti catvāri taṃtre nuttarasaṃjñike /
bājīkaracikitsā tu / rasāyanavidhis tathā /
viṣatamaṃtra punaḥ kalpāḥ śalyajñānaṃ samaṃtataḥ /
ity aṣṭāṃgam idaṃ ta[n]traṃ ādi[f.6r]devena bhāṣitaṃ / [i.e., from
two thirds of the way through adhy.3.

Text continuous up to ff.6r-6v, which have:] yas tūbhayajño
matimāmn sa samārtho rthasādhane //
karmāhave ti starituṃ dvicakraḥ syamaḍano yathā [then skips rest
of adhy.3, and start of adhy.4] // ekaṃ śāstram adhīyāno na
vi(m)dyāt sāstraniścayaṃ [sic] /
tasmād bahuśrutaḥ śāstram vijānīyāc cikitsakaḥ / [i.e., end of
adhy.4]

... sa vaidyo 'nyeti taskarāḥ /
yathā kharāḥ[6v]ś caṃdanabhāravāhī bhārasya vettā na tu
caṃdanasya /

evam hi śāstrāṇi bahūny adhītaś cārtheṣu mūḍhakharavad vahaṃti
// [near start of adhy.4]

iti śrīsauśrute āyurvedaśāstre sūtrasthāne
adhyāyanasaṃpradānīyanāmādhyāyo [=3] dvitīyaḥ // 2 //
athāto 'agnyopaharaṇīyam adhyāyaṃ [=5] vyākhyāsyāma //
trividhaṃ karma // pūrvakarma pradhānakarma /
paścātkarmmeti // [i.e., beginning of adhy.5]

F.7v has: tato gugulvagarusarjjarasabacāgaurasarṣapacūrṇair
lavaṇaṇiṃbapatravvyāmiśrair ājyayuktair dhūpair dhūpayet // [i.e.,
half way through adhy.5]

iti śrīsauśrute āyurvedaśāstre sūtrasthāne
agnyopaharaṇīyanāmādhyāyo [=5] tṛtīyaḥ // 3 // śrī //
athāto viśiṣṭānupraveśanīyam adhyāyaṃ vyākhyāsyāmaḥ //
adhigatataṃtreṇopāsitataṃtrārthena dṛṣṭakarmāṇā kṛtayogyena
śāstrārthaṃ nigaditā rājānujñātena nīcanakharomṇā śucinā
śuklavastraparivṛttena chatravatā ... [adhyāya 10]

F.25v=p.112, start of adhy.30.

26r=Sū.31

27r=Sū.32

29r=Sū.33

30v=Sū.34, but goes straight into 46 (p.200): ata ūrdhvaṃ
māṃsavargān upadekṣyāmaḥ //

37r=Sū.46, end of māṃsavarga (p.206). Goes straight into Nidāna:

37r=Ni.1

43r=Ni.2

69v has end of Nidānasthāna: raktena pittodita eka evaṃ †kaiścit†
pradiṣṭo mukhapākasamjñāḥ //

iti nidānaṃ sthānaṃ dvitīyaṃ //

athāto vyādhisamuddeśīyam adhyāyaṃ vyākhyāsyāmaḥ //
dvidvidhā vyādhyāḥ śāstrasādhyāḥ snehādikriyāsādhyāś ca // [i.e.,
Sū.24!]

72r has end of Sū.24, then: athāto ṣṭavidhaśāstrakamīyam

adhyāyaṃ vyākhyāsyāmaḥ [=Sū.25]// cha // śrī //

'hitāhitīye [adhy.Sū.20]' athāṣṭavātaguṇān vakṣyāmaḥ //

pūrvaḥ sa madhuraḥ snigdho lavaṇaś caiva mārutaḥ //

ru'2'gu'1'r vidāhajanano raktapittābhivardhanaḥ / [i.e., the verses
from the end of Sū.20.] ...

Text ends f.72v: kṣīṇaḥ kṣayaviṣārttānāṃ / viśeṣeṇa tu pūjitaḥ [last
verse of Sū.20]/

iśānakaṭukarūkṣoṣṇaḥ ājñeyāś caiva mārutaḥ /

amlo vidāhīnair atyovāyavyāstikṣa ucyate // śrī ... śrī //

Colophon: bhagnapṛṣṭi kaṭiḥ grīvā / ekavittam adhomukhaṃ /
kaṣṭhena liṣitaṃ śāstraṃ yatnena paripālayet // 1 // śrī // śrīr astu
kalyāṇaṃ bhavatu // liṣitaṃ dharmadāsenā // ciraṃ //
[A red line sets apart the following text in a more informal hand:]
dhanvaṃtari samudra mahānī kalpotivārai svāmi kārṭtikeya
haṃsakair rūpi ho †pūcchyo [[tivāraiṃ pratyttaradīgho]] / ko 'ruk /
varṣā tiṣṭati / śarat pivati / hemaṃte śīśare atti / [[†naṣṭadhau]]
mādhvī pivati / grīṣme svapati / so aruk bhavati vihaṃgamaḥ // //
F.72v has marginal pencilled note: sūtrasthāna 72–9–30 1200

Dravyagūṇaśataślokī / Trimalla Bhaṭṭa Poleman no. 5295. Houghton
Library shelf no. 530b.

Ff.4–28. 13×28.5cm. 5–6 lines, 28 akṣaras. Physically incomplete. .
Found with Brown paper wrapper has: śataślokī – trimallaḥ
pa. 28–5–28 ślo. 350.

. The colophon of this manuscript correctly calls the work the
Śataślokī by Trimalla Bhaṭṭa, and Poleman has followed this
ascription. But leaves 1–3 of the manuscript are from a different
work, the *Ajīrṇamañjarī* by Kāśīnātha. These two works appear
together in some other manuscripts, e.g., Poona BORI (Vaidyaka) 3.

Covers from verse 10 to end of work. Sanskrit interlinear gloss
throughout.

Begins, f.4r: [kra]mād
ekādvitrilavonakaṃ tu pavane pitte kaphe sajvare // 10 //
iti jalavargaḥ
Ends, f.28r: himādrer utpannā samupacitapaṃcānanarasā
dadānā bhaktebhyaḥ pratidivasam uccair amalātāṃ
adoṣā sānaṃdaṃ gadiviracitastotranivahāśivām
enaī rujyaṃ janayatu sadānaṃdajanaiiçñī // 100 //
iti śrītrimallavaidyarājā viracitā iyaṃ śataślokī samāptaṃ // śrīr
astuḥ / śrī

Dravyagūṇaśataślokī / Trimalla Bhaṭṭa Poleman no. 5296. Houghton
Library shelf no. 2227.

Ff.1–4, 6–13. 10.5×24cm. 12 lines, 29 akṣaras. Physically
incomplete. .

Bibliography: Printed at Bombay in 1896, with a Hindī *ṭīkā* by
Śāligrāma Vaiśya; at Benares in 1869 (lithograph); and at Bombay in
1894, with a Hindī translation by Kṛṣṇalāla.

Trimalla Bhaṭṭa was the son of Vallabha, son of Siṅgaṇa (who was famous in Kāśī), of a Tailiṅga family of Āpastambas surnamed Ākhella, from Koḍapalli. He resided in Tripurāntakanagara (N 16° E 79½°). His brothers were Rāma and Gopa, and he had a son called Śaṅkara. Velankar (ABC 33.1, p.59) has given evidence to show that Trimalla lived between 1383 and 1499. See also Meulenbeld 1974, p.419 ff. Variant title: *Śataślokī, Pathyāpathya(nighaṇṭu)* (mistakenly, from these words in the second verse of its introduction).

Covers complete work.

F.1r has, in pencilled Latin script: iti trimallaka viracitā
guṇāguṇaśataślokī [and in ink:] Vaidyak

Begins, f.1v: śrīgaṇeśāya namaḥ //

śrīkaṃṭhaṃ girijāgaṇeśasahitaṃ natvā śaraṇyaṃ satāṃ

Ends, f.13r–v: himādrer utpannā samupacitapaṃcānanarasā

dadānābhaktebhyaḥ pratidivasam uccaiḥ ramalatāṃ //

adoṣā sānaṃdaṃ gadiviracitastotranivahāśivāṃ

enaī rujyaṃ janayatu sadānaṃdajananī 101

iti trimallakaviracitā guṇāguṇaśataślokī

Unidentified nidāna text Poleman no. 5349. Houghton Library shelf
no. 515.

38 leaves. 15–20 lines. Physically incomplete. .

Unidentified saṃnipāta text Poleman no. 5348. Houghton Library shelf
no. 412.

leaves 1–14, 16–18. Physically incomplete. .

Vaidyakakośa Poleman no. 5336. Houghton Library shelf no. 449.

Ff.3–24, 26–30. 12×28.5cm. 11 lines, 35 akṣaras. Prṣṭhamātrā
vowels. Physically incomplete. .

F.3r begins: ktakaḥ /

ariṣṭasarvatobhadraḥ / subhadraḥ pāribhadraḥ /

kuṣṭhāhādevatāgraścaravisannibhasūryakaḥ //

niṃba nāma // //

mahāniṃbaḥ smrto drekā / kārmuko viṣamuṣṭikaḥ /

keśamuṣṭir niravako / ramyā kaḥ kṣīra eva ca //

bakā iti nāmaḥ // //

kirātatiktakohaimaḥ / kaṭutiktaḥ kirātakāḥ //

bhūniṃbo nāryatikta / kirāto rāmasenakaḥ // //

naipālaḥ prathitaś cānyo jātibhedo jvarātakaḥ /
nāḍī tiktordhvatiktaś ca / nidrāriḥ sannipātahā //
cirāyate nāmaḥ //
F.24v ends: // pītari nāmaḥ //
rājarītismṛtā rājñī / rājaputrī maheśvarī /
vrahmā
F.26r begins: dhyāphalo gṛhi / vṛkṣagulmalatānīca /

Vaidyasāgara With *Hindī ṭīkā*

Poleman no. 5335. Houghton Library shelf no. 1363.

FF.1–140. 9×23.5cm. 7 lines, 25 akṣaras. Physically incomplete. .

F.1r has: atha neruroga // murailākapaṣanā 25 gura 25
kūṭigolīkapavaṣāvadina 14 nerū†aturo jvarapitāśleṣajvarajirṇeṣu
vāṃdhavā //

†bhāmakāle kuṭuṃva †[x] dīnakāle ripus tathā // śrīḥ Text begins,
f.1v: śrīgaṇeśāye namaḥ

vaidyasāgara likhyate

namāmi dhannvantarim ādidevaṃ vātātmajaṃ gaurisutaṃ maheśaṃ
//

siddheśvarīṃ bhairavadevasarvvaṃ namāmy ahaṃ

vaidyagathāmanantaṃ // 1 //

aṣṭādaśajvaram caiva sannyaṣṭas trayodaśaḥ

te sarvve te mayā kathyaṃ rājarogādikaṃ paraṃ // 2 //

atha dūtalaḥṣanaśubhā śubhā //

Ṭīkā begins, f.3v: // 15 // ṭīkā // dāha chana śīta ho

hr̥daiduṣaigāṭhihāṭhiduṣaimāthadhumaī kā na māraktacūvai //

Text ends, f.140r: // 51 //

anantapāraṃ kritavaidyasāstraṃ svapnaṃ gamed

aṣṭagaramthanūnaṃ //

dharmāpurimkāśīkamannakāro 'tate sthitaṃ gramtha mayā

prakāśyaṃ //

śubha aśybhoksaṃkhyā 55.

iti śrī anaṃtadaivajñāgramthe sāgare samāptaṃ śubhaṃ bhūyāt

maṅgalam astu //

tadaśaṃvatsara 1840 mārgamāṃsaptāṣṭapache tithau paṃcamyāṃ

bhṛguvāsare kā liṣṭaṃ mansārāma upādhyā ṣemanāthake suta

ātmāpaṭhārthaṃ // śubham astu //

1\12\139

12/

278
139

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F.140v has: atha kāsośvāsaḥ // goghṛtapāvabhani /
rūsapātrapiya†patinakaparasanikarava / kaṇāpai 1 miśrī 6 pai 3 //
sahatapai 3 // tāvapītanikevāssanamācaḍhā
dehaghṛtamelidenājavaghṛta ho . . . tavachanīle pīparima†dhye
uparase ḍārikai piyavavina

Sārasaṅgraha / Yogarāja Poleman no. 5339. Houghton Library shelf
no. 1366.

46 leaves. 9–10 lines. Physically incomplete. .
colophon.